

SEMANTICS OF MORPHONOLOGICAL ALTERNATIONS IN THE COMPOSITION OF A DERIVED WORD

Xasanov Mahmudjan Abduraxmanovich

Senior teacher of Uzbekistan State World Languages University
mahmud.khasanov1961

Karimova Umida Erkinovna

Student of Masters degree Uzbekistan State World Languages University
umidakarimova95@mail.ru

Annotation: *the article gives information about morphonology, in this article the term morphonology refers to the branch of linguistics that studies the use of phonological means for morphonological purposes.*

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Morphophonology is a branch of linguistics that studies the interaction between morphological and phonological or phonetic processes. The term morphonology refers to the section of linguistics, phonological means for morphonological purposes, for example, measures to express morphological differences (Abduazizov, 1992, 67).

Fundamentals of morphology in this sense were laid by I.A. Baudouinde Courtney, having developed the theory of alternatives or alternations of phonemes in morphemes /1963/, even earlier, J.

Grimm was developing a conception of vocalistic alternations. Ancient the Indo-European ablautis considered by him as a phono morphonological phenomenon and worn with later vocalist alternations. Ablaut, umlaut and refraction are considered by him to be elements of a single system, they are functionally meaningful vocalists' alternations / Cited. According to: Desnitskaya, 1985.9.

The theory of alternation I.A. Baudouinde Courtney /1877/ was developed by representatives of Moscow phonological school: N.V. Krushevsky /1883/, P.S. Kuznetsov/1952, M.V. Panov / 1953,

1966, 1967, 1979/, A.A. Reformatsky /1967, 1970/, N.E. Ilyina /1980/, E.S. Kubryakova, Yu.G. Pankrats / 1983 1, O.S. Shirokov / 1985).

The question of the semantics of morphological derivative word alternations, although raised in numerous studies concerning the general semantics of derivatives words, is not subjected to special study there is. The relevance of such a study is by the fact that the derivative word, being these conditions nominative sign, characterize the study has a number of specific features. The derived word is the basis notion is of the word-formation system, analyzing again:

Academic [ˌækəˈdemɪk], academician [əˌkædəˈmɪʃn], politics [ˈpɒlətɪks], politician [ˌpɒləˈtɪʃn], phonetics [fəˈnetɪks]. phonetician [ˌfəʊnəˈtɪʃn], we consider secondary education as derivatives, so as they relate to the corresponding source words, forming an opposition, they are at least two-morphemic in that they include the source words stem and suffix, have formal and semantic

connections and are repeated in a series of words similar in form. In a derived word, its immediate components are distinguished — the stem and suffix, and all accent changes will be considered relative to the stem and suffix.

An example of a morphophonological alternation in English is provided by the plural morpheme, written as "-s" or "-es". Its pronunciation varies among [s], [z], and [ɪz], as in cats, dogs, and horses respectively. A purely phonological analysis would most likely assign to these three endings the phonemic representations /s/, /z/, /ɪz/. On a morphophonological level, however, they may all be considered to be forms of the underlying object //z//, which is a morphophoneme realized as one of the phonemic forms {s, z, ɪz}. The different forms it takes are dependent on the segment at the end of the morpheme to which it attaches: the dependencies are described by morphophonological rules. (The behaviour of the English past tense ending "-ed" is similar: it can be

pronounced /t/, /d/ or /ɪd/, as in hoped [həʊpt], bobbed [bɒbd] and added [ædid], visited [vizətid].)

The plural suffix "-s" can also influence the form taken by the preceding morpheme, as in the case of the words leaf and knife, which end with [f] in the singular/but have [v] in the plural (leaves, knives). On a morphophonological level, the morphemes may be analyzed as ending in a morphophoneme //F//, which becomes voiced when a voiced consonant (in this case the //z// of the plural ending) is attached to it. The rule may be written symbolically as /F/ -> [α_{voice}] / ___ [α_{voice}]. This expression is called Alpha Notation in which α can be + (positive value) or - (negative value).

Comparing the original and derived words directly from the oppositions, we single out the suffix in its specific implementation:

- an [ən] from a Greek-Grecian type opposition;
- ian [j ən] 'Canada-Ca'nadian;

- ian [j ən] 'calendar — calen'darian;
- ician [iʃən] 'beauty-beau'tician;
- itian [iʃən] 'diet — die'titian;
- arian [eəriən] 'celibate-celibat'arian.

The identified variant soft he suffix are considered allomorphs, since they have one meaning — the name of a person engaged in a certain activity, a person living in a certain area: Ca'nadian, Ge'nevan, Gre'cian. Compared segments, which are in relation to additional distribution, are found in analogous constructions.

In linguistics, an allomorph is a variant phonetic form of a morpheme, or, a unit of meaning that varies in sound and spelling without changing the meaning. The term allomorph describes the realization of phonological variations for a specific morpheme. The different allomorphs that a morpheme can become are governed by

morphophonemic rules. These phonological rules determine what phonetic form, or specific pronunciation, a morpheme will take based on the phonological or morphological context in which they appear.

The suffixes [-ən], [-jən], [-lən] are accent conditioning because they determine the presence of stress in the derived word on the syllable preceding the suffix. The main stress characterizes both the original and the derived stems. The suffixes [lən], [ɛəriən] themselves are carriers of the main stress in the derived word. The main stress, in this case, characterizes only the original basis. Thus, the structure of the suffix determines the shift of the stress in the derived word compared to the original one.

Thus, the structure of the suffix — and determines the shift of stress in the derivative word compared to the original.

Comparing the accent characteristics of the original and

derived bases, we derive the following types:

1. Mono syllabic stems sect — sec'tarian;
2. Two-syllable stems 'pulpit — pulpi'tarin;
3. Three-syllable stem spolitics — politician;
4. Four-syllable foundations, mathematics — mathema-tician;
5. Five-syllable foundations meta 'politicsmeta politician.

An analysis of derivatives in — shows that the derived word, in comparison with the original one, has not only a suffix but also certain morphological alternations. The main lexical meaning of the opposition is the word-formation basis — a common part for both members of the opposition. The suffix conveys a generalized derivational meaning, which is specified by the lexical meaning of the stem.

So, the suffix acts as the main means of conveying derivational meaning. Its grammatical function is

that it refers a word to a particular class of nouns.

The results of the study showed that these semantic difference between words can be created by morphological means, and accent changes act as additional means of difference. Since

the place of stress in each word is individual, any change of stress in a certain way signals that the word belongs to one or another semantic group and at the same time indicates its morphological function.

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The IPA provides braces for prosodic notation.

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